

METHOD OF SOFTWARE SELECTION OF OBJECTS BASED ON INTEGRATION OF NAVIGATION DATA AND VISUAL FEATURES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20068133>

Abstract. *This article presents the concept and mathematical implementation of an autonomous UAV control algorithm intended for high-precision positioning relative to an object at the final stage of a flight mission. A method for automatic identification of the object of interest is proposed, based on the joint processing of the UAV's current coordinates, the specified geographic coordinates of the object, and a real-time video stream.*

The main attention is paid to the mathematical model for extrapolating the calculated position of the object into the video-frame plane. The algorithm uses satellite navigation data to form a dynamic "region of interest" (ROI), within which software-based search and classification of objects are performed using computer vision methods. A selection mechanism is described that allows the system to automatically choose the target object from an array of detected targets by comparing their screen coordinates with the target coordinate of the object entered at the route-planning stage.

The developed software solution provides a transition from waypoint navigation to precise visual tracking of the object. Application of the proposed algorithm makes it possible to significantly increase the accuracy of autonomous maneuvering at the final section of the route, compensating for errors in navigation systems and eliminating the need for operator involvement or a stable communication channel.

Keywords: *visual navigation, machine vision, unmanned aerial vehicles, flight controller.*

INTRODUCTION

Relevance of the topic. The current stage in the development of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is characterized by a transition from remotely controlled platforms to fully autonomous systems capable of performing complex technological tasks under conditions where stable coverage of navigation and communication networks is unavailable. One of the key problems in carrying out flight missions at significant distances from the base station is the degradation of communication quality. Limitations in the power of receiving and transmitting devices, the curvature of the Earth's surface, and terrain features often make it impossible to maintain a stable video channel and command-control link on remote sections of the route.

Moreover, dependence on active communication systems reduces the autonomy and interference resistance of UAVs. Constant data exchange makes the system vulnerable to external electromagnetic interference and also allows third-party technical means to detect the location of the aircraft and its owner. In industrial monitoring or search-and-rescue operations, this can lead to loss of control due to industrial interference or deliberate distortion of GNSS signals (spoofing). In this regard, the concept of using UAVs that function solely on the basis of integrating satellite

and inertial navigation systems in a mode without active emission is a priority for ensuring the reliability and stability of the aircraft's operation.

Research problem. Despite their high autonomy, flights based exclusively on GNSS and INS systems have a critical drawback: accumulated positioning error at the final section of the route. The error of standard navigation receivers under real conditions can reach 15 meters, and INS systems are subject to temporal drift. Together, this creates a significant deviation from the calculated point, which does not allow effective performance of tasks that require precise interaction with small-sized objects, for example, targeted cargo delivery or detailed inspection of infrastructure elements.

The existing technological gap lies in the difficulty of ensuring high accuracy when reaching a specified point without the use of external correction. Traditional machine-vision algorithms are capable of detecting objects; however, in the absence of communication with an operator, they face the problem of erroneously selecting the target landmark when multiple similar objects are present in the work zone. A method is needed that will allow a UAV to independently perform intelligent object selection by matching visual data with the parameters embedded in the digital flight mission.

The purpose of this work is to develop an algorithm for autonomous selection and approach of a UAV to an object, which makes it possible to increase the accuracy of technological operations at the final section of the route through dynamic integration of GNSS navigation data and software analysis of the video image.

To achieve this purpose, the following tasks are addressed:

1. Development of a mathematical model for predicting the screen coordinates of the target landmark based on extrapolating data from the flight mission, namely the coordinates of the last route point, into the video-frame plane.

2. Description of an algorithm for the step-by-step transition from navigation by satellite coordinates to autonomous visual tracking of the object.

METHODS

The methodological basis of this work consists of a combination of theoretical modeling and analysis of data from a field experiment. The study applies the method of post-processing video data (post-flight analysis) obtained during a test flight of a flying-wing UAV.

To verify the proposed object-selection algorithm, a test scenario was designed and implemented, simulating the performance of a task in fully autonomous mode.

The logic of the proposed method is based on hierarchical filtering of visual data and includes the key stages of automating decision-making on board the UAV.

1. Initialization of the autonomous guidance phase

The software system switches to active mode when the penultimate navigation point embedded in the mission is reached. At this moment, a descent maneuver toward the target coordinate $T(Lat_t, Lon_t)$ is initiated. This stage is critical for stabilizing the UAV motion vector in the direction of the object, which creates the necessary conditions for the correct projection of geographic coordinates onto the video-frame plane and for activation of the search algorithms.

2. Primary detection and software classification

During the approach, continuous analysis of the video stream is performed using computer-vision methods. The software searches for objects that correspond to a pre-established class, or preset, specified before the start of the mission, for example, "motor vehicle," "building," or "engineering object." At this stage, a dynamic array of candidates is formed, where each object is

characterized by its type and the screen coordinates of its center of mass in the relative coordinate system of the frame.

3. Spatial selection by motion vector

To minimize computational load and eliminate false detections, a method of selection according to the direction of the path vector is applied. Using inertial-system data on the current heading and pitch angle, as well as the current UAV coordinates $C(\text{Lat}_c, \text{Lon}_c)$ and target coordinates $T(\text{Lat}_t, \text{Lon}_t)$, the algorithm determines the calculated direction of the aircraft's movement in the GPS-coordinate plane and in the image plane.

Filtering logic: Initially, the algorithm calculates the azimuth angle of the direction toward the target using formulas of spherical trigonometry, using the current GPS coordinates of the UAV $C(\text{Lat}_c, \text{Lon}_c)$ and the mission target coordinates $T(\text{Lat}_t, \text{Lon}_t)$. The difference between the current heading of the aircraft and the calculated target azimuth determines the required heading deviation.

A linked coordinate system is constructed on the video-image plane, where the center of the frame is taken as the origin. The y-axis corresponds to the pitch angle, or vertical component, while the x-axis corresponds to yaw or heading deviation, the horizontal component.

Object rejection algorithm:

Having calculated the motion vector toward the target in space, the software system projects it onto the frame plane. This makes it possible to divide the entire visible space into a "target sector" and "rejection zones."

Direction criterion: If the calculated motion vector indicates the presence of the target in a certain quadrant, for example, to the lower right relative to the current optical axis, then all objects located in the opposite quadrants are automatically assigned the status of "low priority." In Figure 2, if the motion vector is directed toward objects 2 and 3, object 1, located at a significant distance along the x-axis (heading deviation) and y-axis, will be rejected by the algorithm as not corresponding to the approach trajectory.

Figure 2. Process of software object selection in the video stream. The overlay of the coordinate grid (x — heading deviation, y — pitch) makes it possible to compare the position of detected objects 1, 2, and 3 with the calculated GPS motion vector.

After the primary rejection of objects that do not correspond to the motion vector, the software system proceeds to the stage of coordinate selection of the remaining candidates, in the example under consideration, objects 2 and 3. The task of this stage is to determine which of the detected targets is closest to the true geographic coordinates of the target $T(Lat_t, Lon_t)$ specified in the flight mission.

Mathematical prediction of object coordinates

Initially, the angular deviations of the object center of mass (α_i, β_i) relative to the optical axis are determined. Taking into account the focal length of the lens f and the position of the object on the frame coordinate grid (x_i, y_i), the angles are calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_i = \arctan(x_i / f);$$

$$\beta_i = \arctan(y_i / f);$$

Here, x_i and y_i are the displacement of the object from the frame center in pixels, converted to metric units through the pixel size of the sensor matrix.

At the moment of task execution, the UAV is in the dive phase at an angle θ . With a known flight altitude H , obtained from barometric or inertial sensor data, the horizontal distance L_i , or projection onto the Earth's surface, to the object is calculated by the formula:

$$L_i = H / \tan(\theta + \beta_i)$$

This formula is valid on the condition that the camera is rigidly fixed parallel to the longitudinal axis of the aircraft. If the camera has an inclination angle, it is added to the current pitch angle.

Having the distance to the object L_i and its azimuth direction $Az_i = \varphi + \alpha_i$, where φ is the current heading of the UAV, the increments of latitude ΔLat_i and longitude ΔLon_i can be calculated. In view of the small distances on the final section (up to 500–1000 m), use of the flat-Earth model is acceptable:

$$\Delta Lat_i = (L_i * \cos(Az_i)) / R;$$

$$\Delta Lon_i = (L_i * \sin(Az_i)) / (R * \cos(Lat_c));$$

where R is the mean radius of the Earth.

Final calculated coordinates of the object:

$$Lat_i = Lat_c + (\Delta Lat_i * 180) / \pi;$$

$$Lon_i = Lon_c + (\Delta Lon_i * 180) / \pi;$$

Decision-making algorithm

At the final stage of selection, the predicted coordinates of each object are compared with the reference target coordinate from the mission. The program calculates the magnitude of the error, or deviation, vector for each candidate. The priority target is selected according to the criterion of minimum spatial mismatch.

The final stage of the algorithm is the closing of UAV control on the visual features of the selected object. From the moment of unambiguous identification of the priority target, GPS/INS navigation data cease to be used as the primary information source. The system switches to automatic object-tracking mode, where the main task is to minimize the mismatch error between the center of the video frame and the center of the selected object along both axes.

In real flight, this process is implemented as follows: at the beginning of the dive, Figure 3, when the target is still at a considerable distance, the algorithm continuously selects and verifies candidates. Once the selection is made, control commands are generated for the control surfaces of the flying wing, aimed at aligning the frame center with the target center. This provides high dynamic accuracy: on the final section of the trajectory, Figure 4, the UAV keeps the selected

object strictly in the center of the frame, which makes it possible to compensate for navigation-system error regardless of accumulated GPS error.

Figure 3. Stage of active object selection based on the video stream at the beginning of the approach maneuver.

Figure 4. Stage of visual capture and holding of the object at the center of the frame after unambiguous identification by the onboard software.

CONCLUSION

In the course of the study, a concept of a software algorithm for autonomous object selection and precise UAV approach at the final section of the route was developed and mathematically substantiated. The proposed method makes it possible to effectively solve the problem of insufficient accuracy of navigation systems (GNSS/INS) and eliminate the need to maintain active communication channels, which is a determining factor for ensuring reliable

operation of the aircraft under conditions without external correction and in the presence of electromagnetic interference.

Based on the results obtained, the following conclusions were drawn:

- Improving positioning accuracy: The use of computer-vision methods for trajectory correction at the final stage made it possible to reduce the dynamic error from the calculated 15 meters typical of standard satellite navigation systems to minimum values comparable with the dimensions of the target object.

- Increasing autonomy and interference resistance: Implementation of the algorithm in a mode without active radio emission eliminates the UAV's dependence on external control channels, minimizing the risk of losing control of the aircraft due to industrial interference or distortion of GNSS signals.

- Intelligent landmark selection: The introduction of two-stage filtering — by path vector and subsequent coordinate verification — made it possible to automate the process of selecting the priority object among many similar visual landmarks. This ensures correct operation of the system in autonomous mode when navigating in zones with complex infrastructure.

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